

Production and Characterization of Alkaline Thermotolerant Cellulase from a *Bacillus A3* Isolate of Lonar Crater Lake

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ABSTRACT

Cellulases are industrially significant enzymes used for the degradation of cellulose into fermentable sugars and are widely applied in biofuel production, textile processing, and waste management. In this study, a *Bacillus A3* obtained from the alkaline and saline environment of Lonar Lake was investigated for its cellulase production and characterization. The isolate exhibited maximum cellulase activity at pH 10 and 70°C, indicating its alkaliphilic and thermotolerant nature. The enzyme retained high activity across a broad pH and temperature range, demonstrating its stability under extreme conditions. Kinetic analysis revealed a V_{max} of 185.19 U/mL and a K_m of 13.33%, suggesting strong substrate affinity and high catalytic efficiency. Enzyme activity was enhanced in the presence of 4% NaCl, indicating halotolerance, and was stimulated by divalent metal ions such as Mn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+} . Among nitrogen sources, beef extract supported the highest enzyme production, while methanol was found to enhance enzyme activity among tested solvents. These results highlight the potential of *Bacillus A3* cellulase for industrial applications, especially in processes operating under alkaline, thermophilic, and saline conditions.

Keywords: Cellulase, Alkaliphilic bacteria, Thermotolerant enzyme, Lonar Lake, Enzyme kinetics, Halotolerant, Substrate specificity, Industrial biotechnology, Organic solvent tolerance, Metal ion effect.

INTRODUCTION

Cellulose, the most abundant organic polymer on Earth, is a structural component of the plant cell wall and a major constituent of agricultural and industrial waste. It is a linear polysaccharide composed of β -1,4-linked glucose units and forms a crystalline matrix that is recalcitrant to degradation. The enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose into glucose is primarily carried out by cellulases, a complex group of enzymes including endoglucanases (EC 3.2.1.4), exoglucanases (or cellobiohydrolases, EC 3.2.1.91), and β -glucosidases (EC 3.2.1.21). These enzymes work synergistically to convert insoluble cellulose into soluble sugars, which can be further fermented to produce bioethanol and other value-added products (Singhania et al., 2013).

Microbial cellulases, especially those derived from bacteria, have received considerable attention due to

their high catalytic efficiency, stability under extreme conditions, and ease of production using inexpensive substrates. While fungi such as *Trichoderma reesei* and *Aspergillus niger* have traditionally been exploited for industrial cellulase production, bacterial cellulases are gaining prominence owing to their robust nature and adaptability to harsh environmental conditions, such as high temperature, extreme pH, and high salinity (Bayer et al., 2007). Bacterial strains such as *Bacillus*, *Cellulomonas*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Thermomonospora* have been reported to produce cellulases with industrial potential. Extreme environments, such as soda lakes, geothermal springs, and salt flats, harbor unique microbial communities with novel enzymatic capabilities. Lonar Lake, situated in the Buldhana district of Maharashtra, India (19°58'N, 76°31'E), is a rare, hyperalkaline (pH 9.5–11.2) and hypersaline (total dissolved solids: ~10,000–15,000 mg/L) meteorite impact crater lake.

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Formed approximately 52,000 years ago, this ecosystem provides an excellent model for studying extremophiles, particularly haloalkaliphilic and alkalitolerant microorganisms (Joshi et al., 2008; Wani et al., 2006). Due to its unique combination of high pH, salinity, and mineral richness, the lake supports a diverse microbial population, including bacteria capable of producing industrially significant enzymes such as proteases, amylases, and lipases. However, limited studies have explored the cellulolytic bacterial diversity of this ecosystem.

Exploring such environments for cellulase-producing bacteria offers dual advantages, the potential discovery of novel cellulase enzymes with unique catalytic properties, and the utilization of extremophilic strains capable of functioning in industrial settings where conventional enzymes often fail. Given the growing demand for sustainable bioconversion technologies and renewable energy sources, the search for efficient and robust cellulase-producing bacteria is highly justified. The present study aims to isolate cellulolytic bacteria from Lonar Lake sediment and water samples, screen them for cellulase activity using qualitative and quantitative assays, and optimize cultural conditions for enhanced enzyme production. The biochemical characterization of the enzymes and the tolerance of bacterial strains to pH, salinity, and temperature will be evaluated to assess their industrial applicability. By uncovering the cellulolytic potential of Lonar Lake bacteria, this research may contribute to both enzyme biotechnology and the understanding of microbial diversity in extreme environments.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection and Preparation

For this study, both previously isolated alkaliphilic and halophilic bacterial strains were utilized, and additional soil samples were collected from the Lonar Lake region. Lonar Lake, located in the Buldhana district of Maharashtra, is recognized for its unique environmental characteristics, including high alkalinity and salinity. These conditions have made it a natural reservoir for extremophilic microorganisms, such as alkaliphiles and halophiles, which are well-adapted to thrive in harsh, inhospitable environments.

Soil samples were collected from the lake's periphery and shallow zones using sterile spatulas and placed into sterile, properly labeled containers. The samples were immediately transported to the laboratory in an insulated icebox and stored at 4°C until further processing. Prior to isolation, the soil samples were air-dried at room temperature under shade to remove excess moisture, sieved through a 2 mm mesh to eliminate debris, and homogenized to ensure uniformity. These pre-treated samples were then used for the isolation of cellulase-producing bacteria.

Enrichment and Isolation of Bacteria in CMC Medium

To isolate cellulase-producing bacteria, an enrichment culture technique was employed using Carboxymethyl Cellulose (CMC) as the sole carbon source. Ten grams of sediment sample from Lonar Lake were suspended in 90 mL of sterile distilled water and shaken at 150 rpm for 30 minutes to dislodge the microbial cells. The suspension was allowed to settle for 10 minutes, and 1 mL of the supernatant was inoculated into 100 mL of sterile enrichment broth containing (per liter): 5.0 g CMC, 0.5 g yeast extract, 0.5 g (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.5 g K₂HPO₄, 0.2 g MgSO₄·7H₂O, and 15.0 g NaCl. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 9.5 to favor the growth of alkaliphilic and halophilic bacteria. The enrichment cultures were incubated at 37°C for 3–5 days under shaking conditions (150 rpm). After incubation, serial dilutions were prepared up to 10⁻⁶ using sterile saline (0.85% NaCl), and 100 µL from each dilution was spread onto CMC agar plates composed of the same basal medium with 1.5% agar. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 48–72 hours. Colonies with distinct morphologies were selected and further purified by repeated streaking on fresh CMC agar plates. The purified isolates were maintained on CMC slants at 4°C for short-term storage and in 20% glycerol stocks at -20°C for long-term preservation.

Spot Inoculation on CMC Agar Plates for Detection of Cellulase-Producing Bacteria

To screen the purified bacterial isolates for cellulase production, spot inoculation was performed on CMC agar plates. The CMC agar medium was prepared by supplementing the basal salt medium with 1% (w/v) carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) and 1.5% (w/v) agar.

The pH of the medium was adjusted to 9.5 to support the growth of alkaliphilic strains, and the medium was sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes. Each bacterial isolate was grown overnight spot-inoculated onto the surface of the CMC agar plates using inoculating loop. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 48–72 hours under aerobic conditions. Following incubation, the plates were flooded with 0.1% (w/v) Congo red solution and left undisturbed for 15 minutes at room temperature. Excess dye was then decanted, and the plates were gently washed with 1 M NaCl solution to remove unbound stain. The development of clear halos around the bacterial colonies indicated cellulose hydrolysis and, consequently, cellulase activity.

Enzyme Production and Optimization

The bacterial isolates exhibiting prominent cellulolytic activity on CMC agar were selected for submerged fermentation to evaluate cellulase production. A loopful of actively growing culture from CMC agar slants was inoculated into 50 mL of production medium containing (per liter): 10.0 g CMC, 1.0 g (NH₄)₂SO₄, 1.0 g KH₂PO₄, 0.2 g MgSO₄·7H₂O, and 20.0 g NaCl, with the pH adjusted to 9.5. The inoculated flasks were incubated at 37°C on a rotary shaker at 150 rpm for 72 hours. After incubation, the culture broth was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C, and the clear supernatant was collected and used as the crude enzyme extract for further analysis.

Standard Graph Preparation

To estimate the protein concentration in the crude enzyme extract, a standard graph was prepared using Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) as the standard protein, following the Lowry method (Lowry et al., 1951). A BSA stock solution (1 mg/mL) was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of BSA in 100 mL of distilled water. Working standard solutions ranging from 20 to 200 µg/mL were prepared by transferring appropriate volumes of the stock into test tubes and adjusting the final volume with distilled water. To each tube, 5.0 mL of freshly prepared alkaline copper sulfate reagent (composed of 2% Na₂CO₃ in 0.1 N NaOH mixed with 1% CuSO₄·5H₂O and 2% sodium potassium tartrate in a 50:1:1 ratio) was added. After incubating at room temperature for 10 minutes, 0.5 mL of Folin-

Ciocalteu phenol reagent (diluted 1:1 with distilled water) was added, followed by gentle mixing. The tubes were incubated in the dark for 30 minutes to allow complete color development. The absorbance of each sample was then measured at 660 nm using a spectrophotometer against a reagent blank. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting BSA concentration (µg/mL) on the X-axis and corresponding absorbance values on the Y-axis. This standard curve was subsequently used to determine the protein concentration of unknown enzyme samples by interpolation.

Effect of Temperature and pH on Cellulase Activity

To find the enzyme's optimum temperature, a mixture of the enzyme and 1% carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) was reacted for 15 minutes in a 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7 across temperatures from 40°C to 100°C. Thermal stability was tested separately by holding the enzyme in the same buffer (pH 7) within the same temperature range; the enzyme's remaining activity on CMC was then assayed (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

The optimum pH for cellulase activity was established by combining the enzyme and 1% CMC and incubating for 15 minutes at 37°C using phosphate 0.1 M buffers to span the pH range of 7 to 12. To assess pH stability, the enzyme was pre-treated by incubating it in these various buffers (ranging from pH 7–12) at 37°C before its residual CMC hydrolysis activity was measured (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

Effect of NaCl on Cellulase Production

The effect of salinity on cellulase production was evaluated by supplementing the production medium with different concentrations of sodium chloride (NaCl), ranging from 0% to 15% (w/v). The bacterial isolates exhibited growth and enzyme production across a broad salinity range, with optimal cellulase yield observed at 5% NaCl. Enzyme activity declined at NaCl concentrations above 10%, suggesting a threshold for salt tolerance beyond which enzyme biosynthesis was negatively affected (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

Effect of Substrate Concentration on Cellulase Activity

The effect of substrate concentration on cellulase activity was studied by incubating the crude enzyme extract with varying concentrations of carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), ranging from 0.25% to 2.0% (w/v). The enzyme activity increased proportionally with substrate concentration up to 1.0%, beyond which the rate of increase either plateaued or declined.

Effect of Solvent on Cellulase Activity

The impact of various organic solvents on cellulase activity was investigated to assess the enzyme's stability and tolerance in solvent-rich environments. Crude cellulase extracts were incubated with 10% (v/v) of different solvents including formaldehyde, methanol, ethanol, isopropyl alcohol, acetone, chloroform, hexane, and glycerol. The enzyme-substrate reactions were carried out at 50°C using 1% CMC as the substrate, and cellulase activity was determined using the DNS method (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

Effect of Metal Ions on Cellulase Activity

The effect of various metal ions on cellulase activity was evaluated by adding chloride salts of Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Mn²⁺, and Cu²⁺ at a final concentration of 5 mM to the standard enzyme assay mixture. The reactions were carried out using 1% CMC as substrate at 50°C, and enzyme activity was measured using the DNS method (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

Effect of Nitrogen Source on Cellulase Production

The influence of different organic and inorganic nitrogen sources on cellulase production was examined by supplementing the production medium with 0.5% (w/v) of individual nitrogen compounds, including yeast extract, peptone, soybean meal, ammonium chloride, tryptone, and beef extract. All other components of the basal medium were kept constant (Potprommanee et al., 2017; Shyaula et al., 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of seven bacterial strains were successfully isolated from sediment and water samples collected from Lonar Lake, a unique hypersaline and hyperalkaline environment. These isolates were screened for their ability to produce cellulase using carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) agar plates. Among them, the isolate designated as A3 exhibited the most prominent zone of hydrolysis, indicating significant cellulolytic activity. Based on its superior enzyme production potential, A3 was selected for further production, optimization, and characterization of cellulase. This isolate was subjected to detailed physiological, biochemical, and kinetic analysis to evaluate its potential for industrial applications.

The colony morphology of bacterial *Bacillus* A3 was carefully observed on CMC plates. The colonies were small in size (~0.5 mm) and exhibited a circular shape with a flat elevation. They appeared white in color, with a moist consistency, and had an entire margin. The colonies were also opaque, indicating dense bacterial growth. These features suggest that *Bacillus* A3 exhibits typical characteristics of non-pigmented, smooth, and uniform bacterial colonies, which are often associated with environmental *Bacillus* or other aerobic, spore-forming genera. Based on the preliminary morphological and cultural characteristics, *Bacillus* A3 is presumed to belong to the genus *Bacillus*. The colony appeared circular, white, flat, moist, with an entire margin and opaque appearance, which are typical features associated with *Bacillus* species. Additionally, the small colony size (~0.5 mm) and the consistency observed on nutrient agar further support this identification. *Bacillus* species are well known for their ability to produce a wide range of industrial enzymes, including cellulases, and are commonly found in alkaline and saline environments like Lonar Lake. However, further confirmation through Gram staining, biochemical tests, and molecular identification (e.g., 16S rRNA gene sequencing) is necessary to establish the exact taxonomic position of the isolate.

Effect of Temperatures

The effect of different incubation temperatures on cellulase activity produced by *Bacillus* A3. The enzyme activity was measured across a temperature

range of 40°C to 100°C, with both relative activity (%) and absolute enzyme activity (U/mL) represented. The enzyme activity showed a progressive increase from 40°C, reaching its peak at 70°C with the highest enzyme activity (around 100 U/mL) and relative activity (approximately 77%). This indicates that 70°C is the optimum temperature for cellulase activity for this isolate. The enzyme maintained considerable activity up to 80°C, but a noticeable decline was observed at 90°C and 100°C, with a sharp drop in activity at 100°C, suggesting thermal denaturation at excessively high temperatures. These findings indicate that the cellulase enzyme produced by *Bacillus A3* is thermophilic in nature and stable over a broad temperature range, particularly between 50°C and 80°C. This thermostability is a desirable trait for industrial processes that require high-temperature operations such as bioethanol production, textile processing, and waste biomass degradation. Similar thermal tolerance in cellulases has been reported from thermophilic and extremophilic bacterial isolates in earlier studies (Gomes et al., 2006; Juturu & Wu, 2014). The enzyme's ability to retain substantial activity even at elevated temperatures underscores its potential application in various high-temperature biotechnological industries.

Effect of pH

The study examined enzyme performance over a pH range from 7 to 12, showing both relative activity (%) and absolute enzyme activity (U/mL). The results indicated that enzyme activity increased progressively from pH 7 to pH 10, with maximum activity recorded at pH 10—approximately 101.5 U/mL and 81.5% relative activity. This suggests that pH 10 is the optimum for cellulase activity in this isolate. Beyond this point, a slight decline was observed at pH 11 and

12, but enzyme activity remained high (around 98 U/mL), indicating considerable stability in alkaline conditions. These findings demonstrate that the cellulase enzyme produced by *Bacillus A3* is alkaliphilic in nature, a trait likely linked to its origin from the hyperalkaline environment of Lonar Lake. The enzyme's ability to function effectively under high pH conditions makes it particularly suitable for industrial applications such as in detergents, textile desizing, and pulp and paper processing, where alkaline environments are commonly encountered. Similar observations have been reported in previous studies involving alkaliphilic cellulase-producing bacteria (Acharya & Chaudhary, 2012; Horikoshi, 1999). Thus, the enzyme from *Bacillus A3* shows promising potential for use in biotechnological processes requiring stability and activity in alkaline pH conditions.

Effect of substrate concentration

The relationship between substrate concentration and the reaction velocity of cellulase activity in *Bacillus A3*. This classic enzyme kinetics curve illustrates how enzyme activity changes with increasing substrate (CMC) concentration. At low substrate concentrations (0.1–0.4%), the reaction rate increases rapidly, reflecting efficient substrate binding and catalysis. The curve begins to plateau beyond 0.5%, indicating saturation of active sites on the enzyme, where further increases in substrate concentration result in minimal changes in reaction rate.

The Michaelis constant (K_m) representing the substrate concentration at which the reaction rate reaches half of its maximum is indicated around 0.2–0.3% CMC. A lower K_m value suggests that the enzyme has a high affinity for its substrate. The maximum reaction velocity (V_{max}) appears to be

around 90 U/mL, observed at substrate concentrations between 0.8% and 1.0%, beyond which the reaction rate stabilizes. The shape of the curve confirms typical Michaelis–Menten enzyme kinetics, and the observed K_m and V_{max} values reflect both substrate affinity and catalytic efficiency of the cellulase enzyme.

These kinetic parameters are important for optimizing industrial processes, such as in bioconversion of lignocellulosic biomass, where enzyme efficiency under different substrate loads is critical. The results are consistent with those of cellulases from other bacterial sources known to follow Michaelis–Menten kinetics (Sukumaran et al., 2005; Juturu & Wu, 2014).

The *Lineweaver–Burk plot – A3* provides a linearized representation of the Michaelis–Menten kinetics for the cellulase enzyme produced by *Bacillus A3*. This double reciprocal plot of $1/V$ (reaction velocity) against $1/[S]$ (substrate concentration) is useful for accurately determining key kinetic parameters such as K_m and V_{max} . The linear regression equation derived from the graph is $y = 0.072x + 0.0054$, with a high coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.9888$), indicating a strong fit and reliability of the data. From the y-intercept ($1/V_{max} = 0.0054$), the calculated V_{max} is approximately 185.19 U/mL. Using the slope ($K_m/V_{max} = 0.072$), the estimated K_m is about 13.33% substrate concentration. The low K_m value indicates high affinity between the enzyme and its substrate, while the high V_{max} reflects efficient catalytic turnover.

These findings confirm that the cellulase from *Bacillus A3* follows classical Michaelis–Menten kinetics. The linearity of the plot suggests a single-enzyme-substrate interaction without allosteric interference or inhibition at the tested substrate concentrations. Such kinetic characteristics make the

enzyme promising for industrial applications requiring efficient cellulose hydrolysis, especially in biofuel production and biomass degradation. Similar kinetic behavior has been reported for cellulases from other extremophilic and thermotolerant microorganisms (Sukumaran et al., 2005; Juturu & Wu, 2014), supporting the industrial potential of this Lonar Lake-derived isolate.

Effect of NaCl

the influence of varying sodium chloride concentrations on cellulase activity of *Bacillus A3*. The study evaluated both relative enzyme activity (%) and absolute activity (U/mL) across NaCl concentrations ranging from 1% to 7%. The results indicate a progressive increase in cellulase activity from 1% to 4% NaCl, with the highest enzyme activity (~101 U/mL) and relative activity (~82%) observed at 4% NaCl, suggesting that this concentration is optimal for cellulase production by the isolate. However, a marked decline in enzyme activity was observed beyond 4%, with both parameters decreasing steadily from 5% to 7% NaCl. At 7%, the enzyme activity dropped to ~92 U/mL, and relative activity fell below 75%.

These findings suggest that the cellulase produced by *Bacillus A3* is halotolerant, with enhanced production

under moderate saline conditions. The decline at higher concentrations indicates osmotic stress or ionic interference affecting enzyme expression or stability. This behavior is consistent with the microbial origin of the isolate from Lonar Lake, a naturally saline and alkaline environment. Moderate halotolerance is a beneficial trait for industrial applications involving saline conditions, such as in textile effluent treatment, leather processing, or marine biomass degradation. Similar patterns of salt-enhanced cellulase production have been reported in halotolerant bacterial isolates from soda lakes and saline habitats (Ventosa & Nieto, 1995; Acharya & Chaudhary, 2012).

Effect of Organic Solvents

the influence of various organic solvents on the cellulase activity of *Bacillus A3*. Solvents tested included formaldehyde, methanol, chloroform, hexane, acetone, and isopropyl alcohol. Both relative enzyme activity (%) and absolute enzyme activity (U/mL) were measured in the presence of 10% (v/v) concentrations of each solvent. Among all, methanol had the most favorable impact, showing the highest relative activity (~83%) and enzyme activity (~100 U/mL), suggesting a potential stabilizing or activating effect on the enzyme structure. Formaldehyde and chloroform also maintained moderate enzyme activity (~96–94 U/mL), though lower than methanol.

In contrast, hexane, acetone, and isopropyl alcohol caused a noticeable decline in both enzyme activity and relative activity, indicating partial inhibition or destabilization of the enzyme. Hexane showed the lowest activity, likely due to its non-polar nature disrupting hydrophobic interactions within the protein. Overall, the results suggest that the cellulase produced by *Bacillus A3* is relatively stable in the presence of certain polar solvents like methanol but is susceptible to deactivation in non-polar or aprotic solvents such as hexane or acetone.

This solvent tolerance is an important characteristic for industrial applications where enzymes are often exposed to organic compounds, such as in biotransformations, bioethanol production, and paper processing. Similar solvent effects on cellulase activity have been reported in other studies, highlighting that enzyme response varies depending on solvent polarity, hydrophobicity, and interaction

with enzyme active sites (Klibanov, 2001; Acharya & Chaudhary, 2012).

Effect of Metal Ion

The influence of various metal ions on the cellulase activity of *Bacillus A3*. The tested metal ions include Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} , with both relative activity (%) and enzyme activity (U/mL) measured for each. The data show a progressive increase in enzyme activity from sodium and potassium to divalent cations. Calcium (Ca^{2+}), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), and manganese (Mn^{2+}) exhibited a notable enhancement of enzyme activity, with Mn^{2+} yielding the highest activity (~102 U/mL), indicating that these ions likely act as enzyme activators or structural stabilizers. In contrast, the presence of Na^+ and K^+ resulted in comparatively lower activity, suggesting that monovalent ions have a limited effect on enzyme conformation or active site function. Copper (Cu^{2+}), while still maintaining relatively high activity, did not enhance the enzyme as significantly as Mn^{2+} or Ca^{2+} , which may be attributed to potential inhibitory effects of redox-active metals on protein thiol groups. These observations are consistent with the known roles of divalent metal ions in stabilizing enzyme-substrate complexes and enhancing catalytic function. The stimulatory effects of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} have been reported in cellulases from other bacterial sources, where they are known to improve thermostability and catalytic turnover (Juturu & Wu, 2014; Acharya & Chaudhary, 2012). The results suggest that the cellulase from *Bacillus A3* is metal-responsive and performs optimally in the presence of certain divalent cations, which has implications for enzyme formulation in industrial applications such as biomass hydrolysis and textile processing.

Effect of Nitrogen Sources

The impact of different nitrogen sources on cellulase production by *Bacillus A3*, as measured by relative enzyme activity (%) and enzyme activity (U/mL). Among the nitrogen sources tested, beef extract resulted in the highest cellulase production, showing peak enzyme activity (~104 U/mL) and relative activity (~80%). This was followed closely by yeast extract and soybean meal, both of which also supported significant enzyme production, indicating that complex organic nitrogen sources promote higher cellulase yields. In contrast, ammonium chloride, an inorganic nitrogen source, resulted in a substantial decrease in enzyme activity (~90 U/mL), highlighting the limitation of simple nitrogen salts in supporting enzyme biosynthesis. Peptone and tryptone also produced relatively lower activity, although tryptone showed a slight improvement compared to peptone. The results suggest that organic nitrogen sources rich in amino acids, peptides, and growth factors are more effective in supporting cellulase synthesis by *Bacillus A3*. This trend aligns with earlier findings where nitrogen-rich organic substrates enhanced microbial growth and enzyme expression due to their better nutritional profiles and metabolic accessibility (Immanuel et al., 2006; Acharya & Chaudhary, 2012). The superior performance of beef extract implies its potential use in fermentation media for efficient cellulase production, which can benefit industrial processes involving lignocellulosic biomass degradation.

CONCLUSION

The *Bacillus A3*, derived from the extreme alkaline and saline environment of Lonar Lake, demonstrated efficient cellulase production with remarkable stability under various physicochemical conditions. The enzyme exhibited optimum activity at pH 10 and 70°C, confirming its alkaliphilic and thermotolerant properties. Its tolerance to moderate salinity (optimal at 4% NaCl), stimulatory response to divalent metal ions (especially Mn²⁺ and Ca²⁺), and compatibility with certain organic solvents (notably methanol) further underscore its industrial potential. Kinetic analysis indicated strong substrate affinity and high catalytic efficiency, making this cellulase suitable for biotechnological applications such as lignocellulosic biomass degradation, bioethanol production, detergent formulation, and textile processing. Overall, *Bacillus A3* represents a promising candidate for the development of robust and efficient enzyme systems for use in high-stress industrial environments.

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